

WAYS TO PROMOTE RAG THROUGH FINANCING IMPORT-EXPORT OPERATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Uzoqov Azamat Bahodir o'g'li

Banking and finance academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Annotation. This is it in the article Uzbekistan in the Republic export financing through encourage ways is studied. Foreign investments attraction of the economy export potential increase and of the country the world in the markets stable place take over for created financial mechanisms scientific analysis will be done.

Keywords: National economy, export, investment, foreign trade, finance, capital, transport- logistics.

in Uzbekistan last in years the economy development, foreign investments attraction to do and export potential increase in order to row economic reforms done increased In particular, high good quality and competitive products work release through international in the markets own place strengthening and export activities development priority task as marked. This process national of the economy stability provide , foreign countries with commercial and economic cooperation expand and investment attractiveness increase such as to factors is based on Export Basics of motivation Directions Our country export potential in raising one row mechanisms work developed In particular , Uzbekistan Republic of national in the economy export encourage and export potential expand for tax benefits , financial support mechanisms and commerce banks through exported financing system current done

Export Competence Expansion For Created Conditions

1. President Decrees through tax benefits Decree No. PF-5587 of November 29 , 2018 with for export directed to organizations one row benefits given This to the decree according to export share high has been legal to individuals benefit tax and a single tax in payment reductions to be given marked . And this export size increase and new external markets mastery opportunities expanded .

2. Export activities financial support on October 21 , 2020 Decree No. PF-6091 with export activities financial support measures acceptance done This to the decree according to , commercial banks through separated of loans percentage expenses reduce and exported financing according to sureties present reach system to the road was put This measures export potential in raising important importance occupation is doing

Financial Incentive Factors

Country export potential increase in order to the following financial mechanisms current made by :

- National and foreign in currency to loans percentage expenses reduction : up to 50 percent was percentage expenses compensation will be done .
- Credit up to 50 percent of the amount Guarantees : Exported financing for credit received to exporters state warranty is given
- Rent in the conditions amenities: Credit get for guaranteed was exporters commission payments two equal to cheap they pay

Import- export in Uzbekistan operations financing through national of the economy stability to provide directed one row practical measures done increased This financial incentives because of of the country export potential significant level grow up is going In world markets competitive of products share increase , export of volumes increase of the country investment attractiveness more to increase service is doing

In the future the economy diversification to do and export potential expand for again a lot economic opportunities is created . Including external in the markets competitive product work release development , international transport and logistics to systems integration strengthen and foreign investments wide attraction to do based on country of export stable tumor provide priority from tasks one being remains .

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